

Glasgow coma scale: what is new?

Sujan Agrawal*

¹Department of Surgery. SBRKM Government Medical College, Jagdalpur(Bastar) C.G. PIN 494001 INDIA.

ABSTRACT Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is one of the most devastating types of injury, and it affects all ages. In India as per the report of the ministry of road transport, Government of India (2007) 1.4 lakhs road accident happened in 2007 with 40,612 people killed and 1.5 lakhs people injured.[1] The frequency of head injury in the UK is around 1500 cases per 100,000 populations per year. Annual mortality attributable to head injury is estimated at 9 per 100,000, and it remains the leading cause of death and disability.

In traumatic brain injury, assessment of the patient's clinical condition and that of secondary changes by using the Glasgow coma scale constitutes the mainstay of TBI management. It is a helpful tool not only for quantifying the injury but also to prognosticate. It evaluates verbal response, eye-opening and motor response in a patient with TBI. The new dimensions added to this time-tested scale are the result of the CRASH (Corticosteroid Randomisation After Significant Head Injury) and IMPACT (International Mission for Prognosis and Clinical Trials in TBI) studies.

These new parameters are the reaction of a pupil to light, Age and CT scan findings. The pupillary response is the key indicator of the severity of traumatic brain damage. It is recorded as both pupil reacting to light, one pupil reacting to light or no reaction. The information is combined using a simple arithmetic score (GCS score [range3-15]) minus the number of non-reacting pupils [0, 1, or 2]. It has also been observed that as the age advances (in patients with TBI), the prognosis becomes poorer. The patient's age and GCS-P have an additive effect on the outcome. The probability of mortality and unfavourable recovery, six months after neurotrauma is higher with increasing age. Analysis of CT findings showed that differences in outcome are very similar between patients with or without a hematoma, absent cistern or subarachnoid haemorrhage. The information gained by CT findings has an added value over GCS-P and age alone. It is a simple extension of the original chart by adding these three abnormal CT findings, i.e. none, only 1, and 2 or more CT abnormalities. The essential prognostic features in a patient with neurotrauma can be brought to gather with graphical display. It helps the clinician to support the decision making and to evaluate the risk of good or poor outcome. It also improves the communication of risk among health care professionals, patients, and their relatives.

KEYWORDS Glasgow coma scale, neurotrauma, prognosis, papillary reaction, traumatic brain injury

Introduction

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is one of the most devastating types of injury. It affects all ages; however, the majority of TBI are due to road traffic injuries (RTI) and occurs in young adults of productive age group. As per the report by the ministry of road transport, Government of India (2007) 1.4 lakhs road accident happened in 2007 with 40,612 people killed and 1.5 lakhs people injured. [1] Hence, India is leading the world in fatalities due to road accidents. TBI is also associated with significant socio-economic losses in India as well as in other developing

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons

DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.MOLECULAR-PATHOLOGY-IN-LUNG-

CANCER10.5455/IJMRCR.Glasgow-coma-scale-what-is-new

First Received: December 25, 2019

Accepted: January 31, 2019

Reviewer: Ivan Inkov (BG);

¹Department of Surgery. SBRKM Government Medical College, Jagdalpur(Bastar)

C.G. PIN 494001 INDIA.; Email:drsujanagrwal@gmail.com

countries. [1, 2] Young male has commonly affected the population in TBI. [3-4] In children younger than 15 years, head injury is the leading cause of mortality, but in the elderly most frequent cause of TBI is fall. 69% cases of injury were reported from age group 15-35. [5]

Head injury accounts for 3-4% of emergency attendance, with around 1500 cases per 100,000 populations per year in the UK, of these 300 per 100,000 require admission. Annual mortality attributable to head injury is estimated at 9 per 100,000, and it remains the leading cause of death and disability. Risk factors include male sex, recreational drugs (including alcohol and drug abuse) and youth at the peak of 15 to 30 years of age. This contributes to the overwhelming social and economic impact of the head injury. It is estimated that 2% of US population is suffering a long-term disability as a result of head injury. Road traffic accidents are the leading cause of head injury, being responsible for up to 50% of cases. Other common mechanisms of injury include fall, assault, and firearms. [6]

In traumatic brain injury, assessment of the patient's clinical condition and that of secondary changes constitutes the mainstay of TBI management. The development of the Glasgow Coma Scale is the cornerstone of assessing the level of consciousness and prognostication. [7]

The Glasgow Coma Scale is used to assess three aspects of the patient's responsiveness, i.e. eye, verbal and motor response. Each of these parameters determines the clinical outcome. [8-9]

The total score of all the three parameters is combined to reach a GCS score. The GCS score is widely used as an index to overall brain damage. It is valuable for distinguishing the head injuries of different severity, monitoring patient's progress and estimating prognosis. [10-11] many other methods of assessment were developed to combine the other parameters and GCS, but they have not added any value to either management or prognostication for example brainstem and other physiological features. [12-13]

The pupillary reflex along with GCS score has been found to be especially useful to this historical scoring system for TBI. Using the pupillary reactivity as a valuable adjunct is the result of study of two large databases, i.e. the CRASH (Corticosteroid Randomisation After Significant Head Injury) and IMPACT (International Mission for Prognosis and Clinical Trials in TBI) [14-15] In the CRASH study 10,008 adults with head injury were recruited from 239 hospitals in 49 countries. The IMPACT database contains data from 11,989 patients with traumatic brain injury (TBI), which were collected prospectively from 11 different studies including eight randomized controlled trials and three epidemiological studies.

The New parameters:

1. GCS and pupil reactivity

In the data available from IMPACT and CRASH studies, two parameters are taken into consideration, i.e. the relationship between GCS total score and reaction of the pupil to light, and, Interaction of these two factors and outcome six months after injury. The pupil reactivity score (PRS) depends upon the number of the non-reactive pupil. When both pupils are nonreactive, the PRS is 2. When only one pupil is nonreactive the score is 1. When neither pupil is unreactive to light the score is 0.

The combined GCS-Pupil score is obtained by subtracting the PRS from GCS total score:

$GCS-P = GCS \text{ score} - PRS$. Since GCS total score can range from 3 to 15, a GCS-P thus have a range of possible value from 1 to

15.

It is seen that the decline in GCS score is associated with the increasing rate of mortality and an unfavourable outcome in each CRASH and IMPACT data sets, and also six months post-injury. In the pooled data, the overall mortality is 16% when both pupils reacted, to 38% when only one reacted, and to 59% when neither pupil reacted. Similarly, unfavourable outcome rose from 31% to 79% as pupil reactivity deteriorated. The GCS score and pupil reaction are two important clinical features that provide the most information about prognosis in a head injury patient. [16-18]

It is found that, combining these two feature yield more information than using either alone. The simple addition of pupil information to the GCS score increases the likelihood of the mortality in a patient with a GCS score of 3 from 51% to 74% and the likelihood of unfavourable outcome from 70% to 90% when GCS-P is 1. The combined GCS-P is not intended to replace the role of separate assessment of reporting of each component of the Glasgow Coma Scale and pupil response in the care of individual patients. The GCS-P is simple to implement and at the same time expands the information about the severity of the patient's clinical condition and prognosis.

It cannot determine the pathophysiological mechanism of brain injury. Identifying these mechanisms require further investigations. GCS-P only acts as a guide to performing such investigations. Prognosis is determined by taking into consideration the patient's age, the findings of imaging, presence or absence of other trauma and extra-cranial injuries.

Figure 1: The relationship between the GCS-P and the percentages of patients dead or with favourable recovery six months after injury. Error bars show corresponding 95% CIs. [19].

2. Age of the patient.

The age above 16 was taken for analysis. Increase in the age of the patient increases the probability of death and reduces the chances of favourable recovery. [20] The patient's age and GCS-P values have an additive effect on the outcome. For GCS-P values from 1 to 15, and probabilities of death 6 months after head injury, becomes greater, with increasing age, and for all age groups, the probabilities of death is more significant with decreasing GCS-P.

The combination of GCS-P and age was found to be substantially more informative than the GCS-P, age, GCS score or pupil reactivity alone. In patients older than 85 years with a GCS-P of 1, the rate of mortality is 100%, and the rate of favourable recovery was 0%. There can be n-number of possible combinations of age and GCS-P, so logistic regression method is used to establish a smooth relationship between patient's age and GCS-P.

Figure 2: Percentages of patients dead (Mortality) or with a favourable outcome (Favorable) 6 months following head injury according to patient age at hospital admission. Error bars show corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs). [19]

3. CT character and outcome.

In the CRASH and IMPACT data sets different CT findings are recorded at the time of arrival to the hospital. The CRASH data set notes the following characters in CT scan: [21]

- Presence or absence of normal appearances.
- Petechial haemorrhage.
- Obliteration of the third ventricle and basal cistern.
- Subarachnoid haemorrhage (SAH).
- Midline shift more significant than 5 mm.
- Any type of intracranial hematoma (evacuated or not).

In the IMPACT dataset, the findings were recorded as per Marshall Classification: [22]

- Diffuse injury, no visible pathology.
- Diffuse injury, cisterns present, mid-line shift 0-5 mm.
- Swelling, Cisterns compressed or absent.
- Diffuse injury and midline shift >5mm.
- Evacuated mass lesion.
- Non-evacuated mass lesions.
- Presence or absence of SAH.

It is observed that the method and recording parameters are different in both IMPACT and CRASH database so three main criteria [23-24] are used, as the CT scan findings, in traumatic Brain injury patients, and they are:

- An intracranial hematoma (Evacuated or not)
- Absent cistern.
- Subarachnoid Haemorrhage. (SAH).

The mortality and prognosis are more or less similar when any one or all CT abnormalities are considered. The mortality risk is 10% when there is no CT abnormality. It is 20-28% with one CT abnormality, 38-58% with two, and 61% when all the three CT abnormalities are present. The CT data are informative, both in isolation and in their added value over age and GCS-P.

Discussion

The new development in prognostication and outcome after six months post-trauma is the method of bringing together the four most critical prognostic features, to predict the outcome following head injury. These four features are early GCS score, pupil response, patient's age, and CT findings. This method is easy and does not require much calculation and computation. The other models do not find wide acceptance due to complex calculation and difficulty in implementation. For clinical utility,

a model needs to balance incorporation of key data points and simplicity in use. [25]

For the prognostic model to be useful, they should be presented in a user-friendly manner and have an ease of application in a clinical setup. [26] The GCS-PA CT achieves this aim very well; moreover, they are extensively validated in various studies as the most important prognostic features in head-injured patient. [27]

Age is taken as 16 years and above. The motor score in GCS is the most important factor, but a recent analysis of 54,069 patients with TBI confirmed that all the three component of GCS contribute usefully to prognosis across the spectrum of GCS total score. [19]

The CT findings can be grouped in so many different ways, but to have a practical approach and ease of application they are combined in three categories only, i.e. presence of an intracranial hematoma, an abnormality of basal cistern and presence or absence of SAH. There is no evidence that other imaging features have a strong enough independent influence on the outcome. With the present approach, the CT findings clearly add value to the predictive yield from age, GCS score, and pupil reactivity. It is also seen that simple models perform as well as complex one. [28-29]

The strength of this model: (GCS-P, A, CT)

- This model covers patients at all levels of head injury severity and predicts mortality as well as the functional outcome.
- This study is easy to understand, implement and informative.
- It permits a rapid assessment of neurotrauma patients.
- In clinical settings, the GCS-P is quickly determined by subtracting the number of the non-reactive pupil (the PRS) from total GCS score.
- The GCS-P is read against the patient's age, and an estimate of prognosis is determined.
- The CT findings grouped in three categories helps in further value addition to this pioneering work.
- The simplicity of GCS-PA, along with CT findings, is ideal for application in clinical settings, where it can provide rapid stratification of patients, which guides the clinical decision.
- The chart supports informed communication about patients and other caregivers.

Competing Interests

None

Funding

None

References

1. Samabasivan M. Epidemiology of Neurotrauma. *Neurology and Prevention. Neurol India (Suppl)* 1991;43:9-15.
2. Ramamurthi B. Road accidents, Epidemiology, and Prevention. *Neurol India (Suppl)* 1991;43:9-15.
3. Yattoo G, Tabish A. The profile of head injuries and traumatic brain injury deaths in Kashmir. *J Trauma Manag Outcomes.* 2008;2:5. [PMCID: PMC2464577][PubMed: 18570674]

4. Verma PK, Tewari KN. Epidemiology of Road Traffic Injuries in Delhi: Result of a survey: Regional health forum. WHO South-East Asia Region. 2004;8:1–10.
5. Luerssen TG, Klauber MR, Marshall LF. Outcome from head injury related to patient's age. A longitudinal prospective study of adult and pediatric head injury. *J Neurosurg.* 1988;68:409–16. [PubMed: 3343613]
6. Norman Williams, Christopher JK Bulstrode, P Ronnan O'Connell. *Baily & Love's short practice o Surgery*, 26th edition. CRC Press Taylor & Francis group Boca Raton London New York 2013;pp310-311.
7. Agrawal SN. The Glasgow Coma Scale: A Breakthrough in the Assessment of the Level of Consciousness. *J Tradit Med Clin Natur* 2008;7: 273. doi:10.4172/2573-4555.1000273
8. Reith FCM, Lingsma HF, Gabbe BJ, Lecky FE, Roberts I, Maas AIR: Differential effects of the Glasgow Coma Scale Score and its Components: an analysis of 54,069 patients with traumatic brain injury. *Injury* 2017;48:1932–1943.
9. Teasdale G, Murray G, Parker L, Jennett B: Adding up the Glasgow Coma Score. *Acta Neurochir Suppl (Wien)* 1979;28:13–16.
10. Brain Trauma Foundation, American Association of Neurological Surgeons: Management and Prognosis of Severe Traumatic Brain Injury. Campbell, CA: Brain Trauma Foundation, 2000.
11. Teasdale G, Maas A, Lecky F, Manley G, Stocchetti N, Murray: The Glasgow Coma Scale at 40 years: standing the test of time. *Lancet Neurol* 2014;13:844–54.
12. Born JD: The Glasgow-Liège Scale. Prognostic value and evolution of motor response and brain stem reflexes after severe head injury. *Acta Neurochir (Wien)* 1988;91:1–11.
13. Wijdicks EFM, Bamlet WR, Maramattom BV, Manno EM, McClelland RL: Validation of a new coma scale: The FOUR score. *Ann Neurol* 2005;58:585–93
14. Marmarou A, Lu J, Butcher I, McHugh GS, Mushkudiani NA, Murray GD, et al.: IMPACT database of traumatic brain injury: design and description. *J Neurotrauma* 2007;24:239–50.
15. Roberts I, Yates D, Sandercock P, Farrell B, Wasserberg J, Lomas G, et al.: Effect of intravenous corticosteroids on death within 14 days in 10008 adults with clinically significant head injury (MRC CRASH trial): randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet* 2004;364:1321–28.
16. Braakman R, Gelpke GJ, Habbema JD, Maas AI, Minderhoud JM: Systematic selection of prognostic features in patients with severe head injury. *Neurosurgery* 1980;6:362–370,
17. Marmarou A, Lu J, Butcher I, McHugh GS, Mushkudiani NA, Murray GD, et al.: IMPACT database of traumatic brain injury: design and description. *J Neurotrauma* 2007;24:239–50.
18. Steyerberg EW, Mushkudiani N, Perel P, Butcher I, Lu J, McHugh GS, et al.: Predicting outcome after traumatic brain injury: development and international validation of prognostic scores based on admission characteristics. *PLoS Med* 2008;5:e165.
19. Gordon D. Murray, Paul M.rennan, Graham M. Teasdale. Simplifying the use of prognostic information in traumatic brain injury. Part2: Graphical presentation of probabilities. *J Neurosurg* 2018;128:1621-1634.
20. Hukkelhoven CWPM, Steyerberg EW, Rampen AJJ, Farace E, Habbema JDF, Marshall LF, et al.: Patient age and outcome following severe traumatic brain injury: an analysis of 5600 patients. *J Neurosurg* 2003;99:666–73.
21. Roberts I, Yates D, Sandercock P, Farrell B, Wasserberg J, Lomas G, et al.: Effect of intravenous corticosteroids on death within 14 days in 10008 adults with clinically significant head injury (MRC CRASH trial): randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet* 2004;364:1321–28.
22. Marshall LF, Marshall SB, Klauber MR, Marjan van Berkum C, Eisenberg HM, Jane JA, et al.: A new classification of head injury based on computerized tomography. *J Neurosurg* 75 (1 Suppl) 1991; S14–S20.
23. Raj R, Siironen J, Skrifvars MB, Hernesniemi J, Kivisaari R: Predicting outcome in traumatic brain injury: development of a novel computerized tomography classification system (Helsinki computerized tomography score). *Neurosurgery* 2014;75:632–47.
24. Thelin EP, Nelson DW, Vehviläinen J, Nyström H, Kivisaari R, Siironen J, et al.: Evaluation of novel computerized tomography scoring systems in human traumatic brain injury: An observational, multicenter study. *PLoS Med* 2017;14:e1002368.
25. Yue JK, Vassar MJ, Lingsma HF, Cooper SR, Okonkwo DO, Valadka AB, et al.: Transforming research and clinical knowledge in traumatic brain injury pilot: multicenter implementation of the common data elements for traumatic brain injury. *J Neurotrauma* 2013;30:1831–44.
26. Perel P, Arango M, Clayton T, Edwards P, Komolafe E, Pocock S, et al.: Predicting outcome after traumatic brain injury: practical prognostic models based on large cohort of international patients. *BMJ* 2008;336:425–29.
27. Marmarou A, Lu J, Butcher I, McHugh GS, Mushkudiani NA, Murray GD, et al.: IMPACT database of traumatic brain injury: design and description. *J Neurotrauma* 2007;24:239–50.
28. Reith FCM, Lingsma HF, Gabbe BJ, Lecky FE, Roberts I, Maas AIR: Differential effects of the Glasgow Coma Scale Score and its Components: an analysis of 54,069 patients with traumatic brain injury. *Injury* 2017;48:1932–43.
29. Lingsma HF, Roozenbeek B, Steyerberg EW, Murray GD, Maas AI: Early prognosis in traumatic brain injury: from prophecies to predictions. *Lancet Neurol* 2010;9:543–54.